

STUDY OF TEXTILE FREQUENCY SELECTIVE FOR WLAN APPLICATIONS

A. C. M. Santana¹, G. W. Pereira², A. M. de Oliveira³, N. M. de O. Neto⁴, R. H. C. Maniçoba⁵.

^{1,4,5}Universidade Estadual do Sudoeste da Bahia (UESB), 201911443@uesb.edu.br, nmon@uesb.edu.br, rhmanicoba@uesb.edu.br, Brasil

²Instituto de Computação (IC) - UFBA, guilhermepereira@ufba.br, Brasil

³LabMax - Instituto Federal de São Paulo (IFSP), amanicoba@ifsp.edu.br, Brasil

Abstract - The frequency response of the Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSS) is investigated numerically through the Method of Moment (MoM). The results show that FSS made of periodic arrays of metallic square loop have a constant resonance frequency at 2.41 GHz which is independent of the dielectric used as substrate. On the other hand, the bandwidth varies according to the dielectric properties of the substrate. Finally, our results indicate a drop in transmission near the frequency of 2.41 GHz, suggesting an efficient filtering behavior in this frequency range.

Keywords: FSS; Square loop; Textile materials, Method of Moments.

INTRODUCTION

Frequency Selective Surfaces (FSSs) are typically passive filters consisting of periodic arrays of resonant elements, which can be manufactured from metallic materials etched on a dielectric substrate. When excited by electromagnetic wave, these surfaces exhibit selective behavior in certain frequency bands, so that they reflect or attenuate the electromagnetic waves with certain frequencies [1].

Knowing these characteristics, we analyze the impact of different textile dielectric materials on the performance of frequency selective surfaces (FSS) made of metallic square elements etched on such textile materials. The main focus of this study is the WLAN filtering applications, operating in the 2.4 GHz band, which covers the range from 2400 to 2480 GHz, according to the 802.11b/g/n standards [2].

DEVELOPMENT

The proposed structure of the FSS was modeled using square unit cells etched on the dielectric surface. The Figure 1 exhibits such a unit cell. The analysis of the frequency response (transmission coefficient) of the FSS was carried out by numerical investigation via the Method of Moments (MoM)

Figure 1. Unit cell geometry formed by conductive patch elements (red color) printed on a dielectric substrate (white color).

The adoption of this geometry was based on the previous work of [3], and the structure was modified in order to reach the specific requirements of this present study. The unit cell of this structure consists of a square ring with external dimensions $i = h = 29$ mm and internal dimensions $a = b = 10$ mm, printed on textile dielectrics with a periodicity $T_y = T_x = 30$ mm. These adaptations reinforce the effectiveness of the square loop configuration in the design of FSS. The structure was implemented according to the previously studied dimensions in order to ensure stability and efficiency within the desired operating range. The Table 1 lists the dielectric materials used in this research and their respective properties.

Table 1. Dielectric materials and their respective properties.

Material	Weave	Thickness	ϵ_r	$\tan \delta$
Cotton	twill	0.62mm	2.231	0.0366
Cotton	plain	0.48mm	2.077	0.0314
Wool	plain	0.42mm	1.865	0.0079
Elano-wool	twill	0.64mm	2.053	0.0076
Elano-wool	plain	1.26mm	1.670	0.0073
Wool + PA	twill	1.47mm	1.529	0.0052
Polyester	plain	0.36mm	1.748	0.0044
Viscose + PE	twill	0.52mm	1.707	0.0079
Polyester	plain	0.08mm	2.122	0.0035
Canvas Fabric	-	0.08mm	2.44	0.0568
Jeans	-	0.06mm	1.9	0.008

The properties of material used in this work, such as Canvas Fabric and Jeans, were extracted from the study of the reference [3], while the dielectric properties of the fabrics such as Cotton, Polyester, Viscose + PE, Wool, Elano-wool, Wool + PA and Viscose + PE were obtained from the experimental data reported by [4].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The numerical simulations were performed by the Method of Moments (MoM). Table 2 shows the simulated results to the frequency response of the FSS for different dielectric materials. This table highlights the resonance frequency (F_r), the initial frequency (F_i), the final operating frequency (F_f) and the bandwidth.

Table 2. Results obtained in the simulations.

Material	Fr	Bandwidth	Ff	Fi
Cotton	2.41	1.293	3.1215	1.8285
Cotton	2.41	1.3232	3.1300	1.8068
Wool	2.41	1.3542	1.3542	1.7686
Elano-wool	2.41	1.304	3.1142	1.8102
Elano-wool	2.41	1.3043	3.0913	1.787
Wool + PA	2.41	1.3196	3.0996	1.7800
Polyester	2.41	1.3682	3.1305	1.7623
Viscose + PE	2.41	1.353	3.1234	1.7704
Polyester	2.41	1.3962	3.1605	1.7643
Canvas Fabric	2.41	1.2445	3.1008	1.8563
Jeans	2.41	1.3303	3.1146	1.7843

A notable observation is that the resonance frequency remained constant at 2.41 GHz for all analyzed materials, regardless of the substrate used, confirming their suitability for applications in the 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi band. This consistent behavior is an indicative that the square loop structure is effective in maintaining the operating frequency regardless of the dielectric materials. The bandwidth, however, showed variations among the materials analyzed. These results indicate that the different materials directly influence the bandwidth of the FSS, being a determining factor for the design of frequency selective surfaces. Since each material presents a unique electromagnetic behavior, the choice of dielectric material is an important factor in the performance of the structure operating in the 2.4 GHz band. Figs 2 and 3 illustrate the transmission behavior as a function of frequency for different dielectric substrates analyzed.

Figure 2. Simulated results in terms of transmission coefficients

Figure 3. Simulated results in terms of transmission coefficients

The graphs show the relationship between frequency

(GHz) and transmission (dB) of the textile materials analyzed, with a focus on the 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi frequency band. The area highlighted in green represents the Wi-Fi operating frequency range, centered at 2.4 GHz. This region is emphasized because it is the primary area of interest in this study.

A significant drop in transmission is observed near the 2.41 GHz frequency, which coincides with the operating range of Wi-Fi networks (highlighted in green in the graph). This behavior indicates that the materials analyzed provide efficient rejection of signals in this frequency range, which confirms that the FSS analyzed has potential for applications that require selective filtering at 2.4 GHz. According to the standards of wireless technologies that use the 802.11b/g/n standards [2].

Textile dielectrics offer significant advantages, such as flexibility, lightness, and breathability, making them ideal for applications where the use of rigid dielectric materials is not recommended, for example, in devices with extremely curved structures. Additionally, the malleability of textile materials allows for their integration into environments where traditional devices would be less efficient or unfeasible [5].

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